

Questionnaire

What is your gender?* (1/4)

- Women
- Man
- Prefer not to answer

How old are you?* (2/4)

- 18 - 25
- 26 - 35
- 36 - 45
- 46 - 55
- 56 - 65
- Over 66 years old

What is the highest level of education you have achieved?* (3/4)

- Without studies
- Primary school
- High school
- Non-University Higher Education
- Higher University Education

What is your marital status?* (4/4)

- Single
- Married
- Cohabitant
- Widow(er)
- Divorced
- Separated (a)

Questionnaire

Do you have children? (Multiple answers possible)* (1/3)

- No
- Yes, I have one or more children over 18 years of age.
- Yes, I have one or more children between 13 and 17 years of age.
- Yes, I have one or more children between 6 and 12 years old.
- Yes, I have one or more children but they do not go to school.

Did your child(ren) have to change schools during the COVID-19 pandemic?*(2/3)

- Yeah
- No
- Does not apply

Are your child(ren) still in the same grade since schools closed two years ago due to the pandemic?*(3/3)

- Yeah
- No
- Does not apply

Following →

Questionnaire

Region of Residence* (1/1)

Amazonas

Ancash

Apurimac

Arequipa

Ayacucho

Cajamarca

Const. Prov. of Callao

Cusco

Huancavelica

Huánuco

Ica

Junin

Freedom

Lambayeque

Five

Loreto

Mother of God

Moquegua

Pasco

Piura

A lots of

San Martin

Tacna

Tumbes

Ucayali

Questionnaire

Number of children under 5 years of age living in the home* (1/2)

Number of older adults (65+) living in the home* (2/2)

Following →

Questionnaire

What is your current employment status?* (1/2)

Employee

Independent worker

Unemployed

Housewife

Other:

Are you a teacher?* (2/2)

Yeah

No and no one in my family is.

No, but someone in my family is.

Following →

Questionnaire

Has your employment situation changed due to the pandemic?* (1/2)

No

I was temporarily unemployed

I was temporarily unable to work

I lost my job

Thinking about your household's total monthly income, would you say your household can cover its basic expenses until the end of the month:*(2/2)

With great difficulty

With some difficulty

Quite easily

Easily

Following →

Questionnaire

How would you rate your health on the following scale? The scale ranges from 0 (worst health imaginable) to 20 (best health imaginable).* (1/2)

A horizontal slider with a light blue track. The left end is labeled '0' and the right end is labeled '20'. A white circular knob is positioned at the center of the track.

How would you rate your level of happiness on the following scale? The scale ranges from 0 (worst conceivable state of happiness) to 20 (best conceivable state of happiness). * (2/2)

A horizontal slider with a light blue track. The left end is labeled '0' and the right end is labeled '20'. A white circular knob is positioned at the center of the track.

Following →

Questionnaire

Do you have access to the internet?* (1/1)

Yeah

No

Following →

Questionnaire

Do you have access to the internet?* (1/2)

Yeah

No

You have access to the Internet at: (2/2)

Home

Job

Other:

Following →

Questionnaire

What do you think are the main obstacles for school students to continue their education during a pandemic?* (1/6)

- They don't have computers.
- They do not have cell phones with technology for virtual communication.
- They do not have access to the internet.
- Don't know

How many doses of COVID-19 vaccine were administered?* (2/6)

Select ▼

Do you wear a mask when necessary?* (3/6)

Select ▼

How has the pandemic affected:* (4/6)

Extremely negative Very negatively Negativamente Not really Positivamente Very positively Extremely positively

The health of the children in your family?	☐						
The happiness of the children in your family?	☐						
The development of children in your family?	☐						
Your Health?	☐						
Your happiness?	☐						
Your future projects?	☐						
Your income?	☐						

Are there any other measures we haven't mentioned that you would like to recommend to keep schools open safely? (5/6)

What would be your suggestions for reopening schools and getting learning back? (6/6)

Following →